

1 **High-fat diet results in neoplastic changes in the breast of the female rat.**

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7 Interactions between genes and environment determine a phenotype in normal health and in disease.
8 Modern-day environment, including diet, has immensely changed since the time of the Industrial
9 Revolution, and before that, from the Agricultural Revolution and Neolithic Revolution. We used whole
10 transcriptome technologies here to discover the most significant changes in the mammary gland of a
11 vertebrate model organism following consumption of a high-fat diet. We report that exposure of female
12 rodents to a high-fat diet results in growth factor- and tumor size-related changes in the mammary gland
13 including activation of *Angptl7*.

14 Citations

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Results

Figure 1: High fat diet resulted in key changes in steroidogenic biosynthetic pathways including activation of steroyl coenzyme A desaturase, *Scd1*.

Figure 2: Metabolic changes included cytochrome b5 reductase-like activation.

Figure 3: DNA damage alterations included activation of *Chek2*.

Figure 4: Growth factor and tumor size related changes induced on the mammary gland of the female rat following consumption of a high fat diet included activation of *Angptl7*.

Figure 5: Other changes included induction of a molecule related to an embryonic stem cell marker (CXADR) *CXADRL1*.

Immunologic changes in obese rodents.

Figure 6: High fat diet results in *Cxcl17* activation in the mammary gland.

Figure 7: Obese mice activate *Epsti1* in the mammary gland.

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Methods

GSE290908